

Associations of Personality Traits and Emotional Intelligence In Social Network Consumers via Data Mining Techniques

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Abstract

The present study aims to investigate personality traits and emotional intelligence in young adults' consumers who use social networks to make shopping. Consumer behavior has long been of interest to researchers. Contemporary research on Consumer Behavior considers a wide range of factors influencing the consumer, and acknowledges a broad range of consumption activities beyond purchasing. Nowadays, since online purchases is a daily practice, it is useful to study the behavior of online consumers who are social network users and make shopping via social media. Two basic components that influence consumer behavior are personality and emotional intelligence. Emotional intelligence is both characteristic of personality and intellectual capacity, which a person inherits from the genetic material of its parents and evolves - develops throughout lifetime. Personality' refers to the pattern of thoughts, feelings and behavior that makes each individual separate from others. These affect the way of think, feeling and behaving towards itself and others.

The data were collected by completion of the self-report questionnaire Trait Emotional Intelligence (TEIQue), as far as emotional intelligence concerned, and the Eysenck Personality Questionnaire (EPQ) as far as personality traits of personality disorders concerned. Specifically, for the collection of data electronic questionnaire TEIQue and EPQ were being created through Google Forms service and posted through the website "<http://www.cicos.gr/iccmi2017/aptei>". Then the collected data were selected for analysis, with relevant transformations in order to have a suitable form for the implementation of the respective machine learning algorithms included in the software package R.

Furthermore, the parameters of the corresponding set of algorithms were determined depending on the case of application to produce inference rules. Some of the algorithms implemented according to specific research questions that were applied, were the classification algorithms for the production of decision trees, regarding the four more general factors (welfare, self-control, emotionality and sociability) of emotional intelligence and also personality traits of social network consumers. The results obtained, after weighing and criteria basis, present consumers' rates, which in turn analyze the degree of emotional intelligence and personality traits. Personality and emotional intelligence index can play a crucial role in clarifying consumer behavior of social network users.

Keywords: Personality Traits, Emotional Intelligence, Consumers, Social Networks, R, Data Mining

1. INTRODUCTION

Contemporary research on Consumer Behavior considers a wide range of factors influencing the consumer, and acknowledges a broad range of consumption activities beyond purchasing. Two basic components that influence consumer behavior are personality and emotional intelligence. Personality refers to the pattern of thoughts, feelings and behavior that makes each individual separate from others. These affect the way of think, feeling and behaving towards itself and others. Emotional intelligence (EI) can be defined as the ability to monitor one's own and other people's emotions, to discriminate between different emotions and label them appropriately and to use emotional information to guide thinking and behavior. Trait EI is "a constellation of emotional self-perceptions located at the lower levels of personality." In lay terms, trait EI refers to an individual's self-perceptions of their emotional abilities.

1.1. Eysenck Personality Questionnaire (EPQ)

Various personality theories have been proposed. Of these, special mention has already been made in so-called "theories of traits". Such have been formulated by Allport, Guilford, Cattell and Eysenck. These are different theories with common trait the factorial analysis of the characteristics and traits of the personality, as these are derived from a person's behavior. In this spirit, Eysenck's theory is about. It came from a combination of the description of Kant's personality traits in relation to Wundt's four idiosyncrasies and system dimensions and to some elements of Galen's theory and can be represented schematically as follows:

The diagram proposed by Eysenck in 1947 distinguished the two basic dimensions of the personality, represented by two intersecting axes. At the two poles of the vertical axis, the maximum and minimum values of the dimension that Eysenck called "Emotionality or Instability or Neuroticism" were placed. The maximum value represented the existence of characteristics of instability, neuroticism, while the minimum referred to the existence of characteristics of emotional stability. On the horizontal axis, the other dimension of the personality was placed, the Inwardness - Extraversion. As on the vertical axis, the maximum value was referring to the personality traits of the extroverted type, as opposed to the other pole, that of the minimum value, which set the characteristics of introversion.

Image 3

The personality dimensions introduced by Eysenck are separate types of people, each of which involves a set of features traced back to their habits and their specific reactions. In particular, what is proposed is the detection of specific reactions of the individual, which will give evidence of his usual reactions and hence of his usual behavior. This will allow conclusions to be drawn for some key features of his personality. These attributes are considered as the factors that make up each of the three dimensions of personality (types). The relationship between the reactions and their regular appearance makes them reliable criteria for rendering certain characteristics to the personality of the person. That is, dimensions or types of personality are notions that include a group of related characteristics, which we deduce from the study of reactions and behavior of the individual.

1.1.1. Description of psychometric scale EPQ

In detail, the three dimensions of the personality that are proposed have the following characteristics:

Extraversion-introversion: One who is defined as extrovert is social, loves gatherings, has many friends, and does not like reading and studying. Also, has a keen desire for emotion, does not lose opportunities, likes danger, reacts immediately and is generally impulsive. The typical introvert is quiet, isolated, intuitive who prefers books from people, is restrained and stays in a distance, except for very close friends and does not love intense emotions, also treats everyday problems seriously and prefers well-planned life, controls his feelings, is trustworthy, pessimistic and attaches great importance to moral values. Extroverted and introverted differ in their behavior and beliefs.

Neurotism - Instability - Emotional Stability: Neurotism refers to the general emotional instability of the individual, to its emotional hyperactivity and to the tendency to develop neurotic symptoms under stress. People with high neurotic values are anxious, sad, sad, and often sad. When neurotism is accompanied by high

extroversion then the person is irritable, restless, even aggressive. Low prices, on the contrary, refer to an emotionally stable person with mild reactions and a generally stable system of values, attitudes and behavior.

Psychoticism: Further exploration of Eysenck's personality dimensions has led to the observation that there is one more personality variable that manifests in the population as a whole - that is, in healthy and divergent - in the form of reaction patterns and is indicative of the possible appearance of psychotic elements. This variable was the third personality dimension, called "Psychotism" (P) and also refers to subjective personality traits. This predisposition exists to varying degrees in all individuals, and only its very high value may be an indication of some form of psychosis. The result of these observations was the development of a measurement scale of the three dimensions of the personality (E, N, P) and a complementary dimension of the L, which measures the falsehood of the answers given by the person questioned during the questionnaire. The new scale, presented by the Eysenck couple in 1975, was named the Eysenck Personality Questionnaire (E.P.Q.).

1.2. Trait Emotional Intelligence (EI)

For recording, tracing and evaluation concerning the emotional intelligence was used the standardized scale Trait Emotional Intelligence (TEIQue) which examines the Trait model of EI as proposed by K.V. Petrides. The Trait Emotional Intelligence Questionnaire is a self-report questionnaire that has been developed to cover the trait EI sampling domain comprehensively. Questionnaire measures of EI have been proliferating over the past few years, and it is important to mention three advantages of the TEIQue over them to justify the focus of this research. First, the TEIQue is based on a psychological theory that integrates the construct into mainstream models of differential psychology. Second, the TEIQue provides comprehensive coverage of the 15 facets of the trait EI sampling domain. Several independent studies have demonstrated the ability of the TEIQue to predict criteria (outcomes) significantly better than other questionnaires. Third, the full TEIQue has excellent psychometric properties. Finally, the TEIQue has been used in numerous studies wherein the assessment of affective aspects of personality was required. These include research in the areas of neuroscience, relationship satisfaction, psychopathology, addictions, reaction time, general health, and behavioral genetics. The TEIQue provides an operationalization for the model of Petrides and colleagues that conceptualizes EI in terms of personality. The test encompasses 15 subscales organized under four factors: well-being, self-control, emotionality and sociability.

Image 4

1.2.1. Description of psychometric scale EI

Well being: The Well-being factor comprises three different traits: Happiness, Optimism and Self-esteem. They measure how people judge their general level of life satisfaction. Well-being reflects people's perceptions of how cheerful and content they usually feel, whether they are optimistic about the future and how much they value themselves.

Self control: The Self-control factor describes how far people think they can control their impulses or are controlled by them. It comprises three different traits: Impulse Control, Stress Management and Emotional Regulation.

Emotionality: The Emotionality factor comprises four different traits: Empathy, Emotion Perception, Emotion Expression and Relationships. Together they indicate how aware you may be of your own emotions and feelings, as well as those of other people. Scores on these traits tend to reflect how highly you value this 'emotional literacy' and when and how you make use of it. Self-aware people, who use emotionality in a balanced way, respond compassionately towards the emotions and feelings of others at the right time.

Sociability: The Sociability factor describes how comfortable people feel in different social contexts, from parties and social gatherings to formal business meetings. In completing the questionnaire, you have suggested how confident you feel in dealing with diverse sorts of people, how far you believe you influence others, and how comfortable you are in arguing your corner. The Sociability factor is a combination of Emotion Management, Assertiveness and Social Awareness traits.

2. METHODOLOGY

In this paper were applied Machine Learning and Data Mining methods in order to evaluate the personality dimensions (EPQ) with emotional intelligence quotient (TEIQue) of social network consumers. The methodology, that was adopted, consists of three concrete phases. During the first phase electronic questionnaires were created and posted through the website <http://www.cicos.gr>. Subsequently, data were collected and preprocessed from the questionnaires. The data set for analysis was consisted of demographics elements of responders, such as the gender, the birth-place, the place of present residence, educational background of both the respondents and their parents, professional occupation of parents and also of subscales of the EPQ and TEIQue tests. During the third phase, the data set was analyzed based on Data Mining techniques and evaluate the results. More specifically, we utilized classification algorithms so as to manage to describe the hidden patterns underlying in the data. Decision trees are a powerful way in order to represent and facilitate statements analysis (psychological) principally, comprising successive decisions and variable results in a designated period.

2.1. Personality, Emotions and Decision-Making in Consumer Behavior

In international literature, the importance of emotion and traits of personality in decision making has been studied (Gohm and Clore, 2002; Luce 1998; Ruth 2001). The research is about to fully understand how consumers' use emotional information to make effective decisions according to their traits of personality. A growing body of research continues to focus on the emotions present in consumption situations; however a better understanding of emotional processing abilities can have important effects on consumer performance outcomes. The current research focuses on emotional intelligence, in personality of consumer and in consumer behavior of young adults who are social network users.

Consumer emotional intelligence is defined here as a person's ability to use emotional information to achieve a desired consumer outcome, comprised as a set of first order emotional abilities that allow individuals to recognize the meanings of emotional patterns that underlie consumer decision making and to reason and solve problems on the basis of them (Mayer and Salovey 1997). A better understanding of emotional ability can have considerable value in extending knowledge of consumer behavior. For example, it can provide answers to questions such as; how does emotional processing influence purchase decisions; which decisions do high vs. low EI consumers more readily make; how might EI influence relationships between key consumer variables such as impulsivity and purchase intention? Additionally, with this knowledge of emotional ability, we may be able to identify those consumer's who make the highest (and lowest) quality consumer decisions. For instance, consumers with high levels of nutrition knowledge who lack the emotional ability to understand which emotions are important and how to manage those emotions toward unhealthy eating, are likely to make poor quality decisions. Understanding these emotional deficiencies can provide a means to subsequently improve the quality of consumption decisions.

As far as the repercussion of personality traits in consumer behavior, recent advances in personality psychology can help us predict consumer motivation. Traits are defined as enduring and stable patterns of behavior, attitudes, emotions, that vary between individuals. Traditionally, researchers were interested in understanding how individuals differ, and so they put a great deal of effort into discovering how to measure, map, and define personality traits. An effort was made through trait theory in order to define personality traits. Trait theory suggests that personality is made up of a set of quantitative measurable characteristics or units known as traits. Traits are pre-dispositional attribute and are relatively stable (McLeod, 2014). Every personality has a unique combination of traits and given its stability, people with a given combination of traits can be expected to behave consistently across situations and over time. The development of trait theory is attributed to the pioneering works of psychologists such as, Gordon Allport, Henry Odbert Raymond Cattell and Hans Eysenck (Myers, 1995; Burger, 2000; Franzoi, 2002). The trait theory that is being examined through the current paper is Eysenck's theory. Eysenck (1947) developed a model of personality based on three traits: "introversion/extroversion, neuroticism/emotional stability, and psychoticism" (Franzoi, 2002: 398).

Researchers are now reconceptualizing what traits are and where they come from--with traits being understood as chronic motivators that drive their decision-making. For example, researchers have linked personality traits to diverse outcomes such as experiential buying tendencies, political orientation, natural language use, preference in pets, the state of one's personal living space, and even more important life outcomes such as divorce, morbidity, and occupational attainment. Some recent data suggests that people who find themselves in disease-ridden environments tend to be less open and extraverted, presumably because this makes them less motivated to explore and interact with others (which reduces the chance they will become infected).

2.2. Data Mining Techniques

Data Mining is an emerging knowledge discovery process of extracting previously unknown, actionable information from very large scientific and commercial databases. It is imposed by the explosive growth of such databases. Usually, a data mining process extracts rules by processing high dimensional categorical and/or numerical data. Classification, clustering and association are the most well known data mining tasks. Classification is one of the most popular data mining tasks. Classification aims at extracting knowledge which can be used to classify data into predefined classes, described by a set of attributes. The extracted knowledge can be represented using various schemas. Decision trees, "if-then" rules and neural networks are the most popular such schemas. A lot of algorithms have been proposed in the literature for extracting classification rules from large relational databases, such as symbolic learning algorithms including decision trees algorithms (e.g. C4.5) and rule based algorithms (e.g. CN2), connectionist learning algorithms (e.g. back{propagation networks), instance-based algorithms (e.g. PEELS) and hybrid algorithms. Association rules can be used to represent frequent patterns in data, in the form of dependencies among concepts attributes. In this paper, we consider the special case, that is known as the market basket problem, where concepts-attributes represent products and the initial database is a set of customer purchases (transactions).

3. RESULTS

Classification methods aim to identify the classes from some descriptive traits. They find utility in a wide range of human activities and particularly in automated decision making. Decision trees are a very effective method of supervised learning. It aims is the partition of a dataset into groups as homogeneous as possible in terms of the variable to be predicted. It takes as input a set of classified data, and outputs a tree that resembles to an orientation diagram where each end node (leaf) is a decision (a class) and each non- final node (internal) represents a test. Each leaf represents the decision of belonging to a class of data verifying all tests path from the root to the leaf. The tree is simpler, and technically it seems easy to use. In fact, it is more interesting to get a tree that is adapted to the probabilities of variables to be tested. Mostly balanced tree will be a good result. If a sub-tree can only lead to a unique solution, then all sub-tree can be reduced to the simple conclusion, this simplifies the process and does not change the final result. Ross Quinlan worked on this kind of decision trees. Decision trees are built in "ctree (Conditional Inference Trees)" by using a set of training data or data sets. At each node of the tree, "ctee" chooses one attribute of the data that most effectively splits its set of samples into subsets enriched in one class or the other. Its criterion is the normalized information gain (difference in entropy) that results from choosing an attribute for splitting the data. The attribute with the highest normalized information gain is chosen to make the decision. During the construction of the decision tree, it is possible to manage data for which some attributes have an unknown value by evaluating the gain or the gain ratio for such an attribute considering only the records for which this attribute is defined. Using a decision tree, it is possible to classify the records that have unknown values by estimating the probabilities of different outcomes. Ctree builds decision trees from a set of training data in the same way as ID3 or C4.5, using the concept of information entropy.

The training data is a set $S = s_1, s_2, \dots$ of already classified samples. Each sample s_i consists of a p -dimensional vector $(x_{1,i}, x_{2,i}, \dots, x_{p,i})$, where the x_j represent attribute values or features of the sample, as well as the class in which s_i falls. At each node of the tree, "ctree" chooses the attribute of the data that most effectively splits its set of samples into subsets enriched in one class or the other. The splitting criterion is the normalized information gain (difference in entropy). The attribute with the highest normalized information gain is chosen to make the decision.

The "ctree" algorithm then recurs on the smaller sublists. In order to specify the best result, it was necessary to fit the data to the model in a proper way. This task was carried away by changing and testing the controls of "ctree".

The parameters in the control function that were altered are:

Figure 5

- mincriterion: The value of the test statistic (for testtype == "Teststatistic"), or 1 - p-value (for other values of testtype) that must be exceeded in order to implement a split.
- minsplit: The minimum sum of weights in a node in order to be considered for splitting.
- mtry: The number of input variables randomly sampled as candidates at each node for random forest like algorithms.
- maxdepth: The maximum depth of the tree.

Tree 1

- ✓ Depended variable: birthyear
- ✓ Independed variables: sex, well_being, sociability, emotionality, self_control
 - 'mincriterion' value: 0.09
 - 'minsplit' value: 50L
 - 'mtry' value: Inf (Infinite)
 - 'maxdeph' value: Inf (Infinite)

Tree 2

- ✓ Depended variable: birthyear
- ✓ Independed variables: Rest
 - 'mincriterion' value: 0.009
 - 'minsplit' value: 50L
 - 'mtry' value: Inf (Infinite)
 - 'maxdeph' value: Inf (Infinite)

Figure 6

3.1. Mining Association Rules

Association Rule Mining is a common technique used to find associations between many variables. In Data Mining, Apriori is a classic algorithm for learning association rules. Apriori is designed to operate on databases containing transactions (for example data collected from surveys in this case). As is common in association rule mining, given a set of item sets, the algorithm attempts to find subsets which are common to at least a minimum number C of the itemsets.

Apriori uses a "bottom up" approach, where frequent subsets are extended one item at a time, and groups of candidates are tested against the data. The algorithm terminates when no further successful extensions are found. Apriori uses breadth-first search and a tree structure to count candidate item sets efficiently. It generates candidate item sets of length k from item sets of length k - 1. Then it prunes the candidates which have an infrequent sub pattern. According to the downward closure lemma, the candidate set contains all frequent k-length item sets. After that, it scans the transaction database to determine frequent item sets among the candidates.

Association rules present association or correlation between item sets. An association rule has the form of $A \rightarrow B$, where A and B are two disjoint item sets.

The Goal: studies whether the occurrence of one feature is related to the occurrence of others.

Three most widely measures for selecting interesting rules are:

Support is the percentage of cases the data that contains both A and

used

in B,

Figure 7

Confidence is the percentage of cases containing A that also contain B, and

Lift is the ratio of confidence to the percentage of cases containing B.

3.2. Apriori rules visualization

Figure 8

Parallel coordinate charts are a visualization that consists of N amount of vertical axes, each representing a unique data set of 61 rules, with lines drawn across the axes. The lines show the relationship between the axes, much like scatter plots, and the patterns that the lines form indicates the relationship. We can also gather details about the relationships between the axes when you see the clustering of lines. Let's take a look at this using the chart below as an example. Specifically of our use, the parameters that were altered are:

- control=list(reorder=TRUE)

Apriori rules

For the top 61 rules that were extracted from the apriori the following parameters were altered:

- support: A numeric value for the minimal support of an item set
- confidence: A numeric value for the minimal confidence of rules/association hyperedges

Specifically of our use: Support: 0.5, Confidence: 0.9

After the extraction, the top 12 rules, also, presented lift approximately 1.

lhs	rhs	support	confidence	lift
Age=[18-23], L_Lie.Social.Desirability=LOW, self_control=HIGH,sociability=LOW =>	{E_Extraversion.Introversion=LOW}	0.1097561	0.9000000	1.447059
{Age=[18-23], Mother_job=Housekeeping, well_being=HIGH, sociability=LOW} =>	{E_Extraversion.Introversion=LOW}	0.1097561	0.9000000	1.447059
Sex=Female, Mother_edu=Higher Education, self_control=HIGH} =>	{E_Extraversion.Introversion=LOW}	0.1097561	0.9000000	1.447059
{Mother_job=Public Servant, self_control=HIGH} =>	{E_Extraversion.Introversion=LOW}	0.1097561	0.9000000	1.447059
{Education=Higher Education, P_Psychoticism.Socialisation=LOW, N_Neuroticism.Stability=HIGH, sociability=LOW} =>	{E_Extraversion.Introversion=LOW}	0.1219512	0.9090909	1.461676
{City=CEPHALONIA, L_Lie.Social.Desirability=LOW, self_control=HIGH} =>	{E_Extraversion.Introversion=LOW}	0.1219512	1.0000000	1.607843
{Education=Higher Education, N_Neuroticism.Stability=HIGH, self_control=LOW, sociability=LOW} =>	{E_Extraversion.Introversion=LOW}	0.1219512	1.0000000	1.607843

- **Grouped Matrix plot**

Antecedents (columns) in the matrix are grouped using clustering. Groups are represented as balloons in the matrix.

- **Graph**

Represents the rules (or itemsets) as a graph. Specifically of our use, the parameters that were altered are:

- control=list(type="items")

- **Paracoord**

Parallel coordinates plot for 100 rules

Figure 9

{Sex=Female, Age=[18-23], City=ATHENS, sociability=LOW} => {N_Neuroticism.Stability=HIGH} 0.1219512 1.0000000 2.050000

{Sex=Female, Age=[18-23], self_control=HIGH, emotionality=HIGH} => {N_Neuroticism.Stability=LOW} 0.1341463 1.0000000 1.952381

{Age=[18-23], City=ATHENS, sociability=LOW} => {N_Neuroticism.Stability=HIGH} 0.1341463 0.9166667 1.879167

{City=ATHENS, Father_job=Retired,well_being=HIGH, self_control=HIGH} => {N_Neuroticism.Stability=HIGH} 0.1219512 0.9090909 1.863636

{Age=[18-23], City=CEPHALONIA, self_control=HIGH, emotionality=HIGH} => {N_Neuroticism.Stability=LOW} 0.1219512 0.9090909 1.774892

4. CONCLUSION

One general determination of the results can be exported in order to conclude and explain the consumer behavior of young adults in social networks. This paper can be a useful tool in the field of Marketing in order to decode psychological issues of young adulthood in the sector of emotional intelligence between males and females.

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